

INTEGRATING CLIA-MODEL (COMPETENCE, LEARNING, INTERVENTION, ASSESSMENT) IN MATHEMATICS LEARNING MODULE AND THE ENHANCED MATHEMATICAL THINKING SKILLS OF GRADE 8 STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The CLIA framework is in line with the new international perspectives on the goals and the nature of Mathematics education as manifested in reform documents such as the Principles and Standards for School Mathematics. Mathematical thinking skills are a lot more than just being able to do arithmetic or solve algebra problems. This study attempted to integrate the CLIA-model in the mathematics learning module in enhancing the mathematical thinking skills of Grade 8 students. This study used a descriptive developmental research design participated by eighty-five (85) students under modular distance learning. The mean scores were analyzed, and the respondents' perception of the degree of importance of the CLIA model was necessary. Meanwhile, the findings of the study on the level of acceptability on the utilization of the mathematics learning module resulted as moderately acceptable in terms of content, adaptability, validity, usability, and appropriateness. The learners' level of Mathematical thinking skills improved significantly after the utilization of the learning module. The learners obtained an outstanding result in both problem-solving and reflecting, which means that the students developed the ability to solve problems with training, explain the importance of findings, and demonstrate them with new representations. In reasoning and proving, inferencing and interpreting results are satisfactory. However, respondents did not meet expectations in hypothesizing, making formulating statements using mathematical language least mastered. There is no significant relationship between utilizing the CLIA Model in the Mathematics Learning module and the level of Mathematical Thinking Skills; and between the evaluation of the Mathematics Learning Module and Mathematical Thinking Skills. There is a significant difference between the level of Mathematical Thinking Skills before and after utilizing the CLIA Model in a Mathematics Learning module.

Keywords: CLIA Model, Mathematical Thinking Skills, Mathematics Learning Module